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A STUDY ON CONVERSION OF INTRAVENOUS TO ORAL ANTIBIOTICS AT A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL, TUMAKURU: AN OBSERVATIONAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To assess the type of conversion therapy from intravenous to oral antibiotics among hospitalized patients and the criteria preferred for conversion therapy. **Materials and Methods:** This observational study conducted for a period of 6 months at SHRC Tumakuru, Karnataka. A total of 127 patients from the hospital's inpatient department were included in the study. The data were collected, analyzed, and interpreted using descriptive statistics. **Results:** Among 127 cases, 100 (78.74%) patients were converted and 27 (21.26%) patients were not converted, males (55.12%) are more suffered, and the age group above 60 years (33.07%) are more hospitalized. Cephalosporin (53.93 %) antibiotics were the commonly prescribed class of drug in which ceftriaxone (54.00%) was preferred. Among the conversion therapy, step-down therapy (43.00 %) was commonly used. T-test revealed that there exists no statistical difference in length of hospital stay (P value 0.5360) and duration of IV therapy (P value 0.2501) among converted and non-converted groups. 10% of patients had a conversion of antibiotics from Broad spectrum to narrow spectrum, Both Patient stability and plan for discharge were found to be 100% respectively. **Conclusion:** Our study concludes that male patients are more hospitalized and systemic fever is most common. Step down was the commonly preferred type of conversion to treat patients. Cephalosporin antibiotics are preferred in patients for both IV and oral routes to treat disease conditions. Clinical pharmacist needs to review the conditions of patients for early conversion of IV to oral antibiotics to prevent irrational use of antibiotics.

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INTRODUCTION BACKGROUND

It is widely acknowledged that the world tackles infectious diseases. Antibiotics development inspired hope that infections could be managed and avoided. However, in the developing nations, infections continue to be the main cause of death. This is brought about by the advent of new illnesses, the resurgence of illnesses that were previously under control, and, more especially, the establishment of antibiotic resistance. Antimicrobial resistance seems to develop inexorably to practically every new medicine, and it is acknowledged as a significant issue in the management of microbial illnesses in both hospitals and the general population.

Intravenous to oral (IV to PO) move therapy is a medical process used to move from intravenous to oral pharmaceutical delivery. The approach entails initiating intravenous therapy in hospitalized patients and reducing it as quickly as feasible to oral medication.

The majority of doctors use intravenous (IV) antibiotics first to treat severe infections in hospitals to guarantee an ideal concentration of medicines at the site of infection. Antimicrobial resistance is known to be mostly fueled by improper antibiotic usage. Unnecessarily long IV antibiotic courses are linked to longer hospital stays, higher costs for nursing, pharmacy, and medical time spent inserting IV lines, preparing, dispensing, and administering IV agents, as well as higher morbidity and mortality rates related to IV-line infections. In the right patient, switching from IV antibiotics to oral treatment provides various benefits for maximizing antibiotic usage.

For the effective conversion of IV to oral antimicrobial medicines, a multidisciplinary medical team must take into account three crucial criteria, including good patient selection, a suitable treatment strategy, and patient health education. An expert in infectious diseases must assess the patient and determine whether switching from IV to oral medication is appropriate. This may finally result in an early discharge and lessen the patient's financial burden.

Criteria for switching from IV to oral treatment.

- Ease of administration as preferable
- Clinical improvement of the patient, stable hemodynamics, and a decrease in white blood cells.
- Taking and absorbing oral medications is possible for the patient.
- Pathogen remains unknown to be resistant to the oral antibiotic to be used
- Reduced risk of cannula-related infections: A cannula must be inserted in order to provide IV drugs; this cannula stays in place for a few days and may eventually develop secondary infections brought on by germs and fungus. This might ultimately result in the patient needing more antibiotics and incurring greater costs.
- No risk of thrombophlebitis
- Less costly than IV therapy: The majority of commercially accessible oral drugs are less expensive since parenteral treatments must be sterile and isotonic, saving the patient money
- Reduction of hidden expenses: Diluents, administration equipment, needles, syringes, and nursing time are the key examples of hidden costs. The necessary equipment for parenteral administration includes needles, syringes, diluents, and other tools. Above important, the injection must be given by a qualified physician. As a result, it might put financial strain on the patient and rob nurses of crucial time for patient care.
- Earlier discharge.

TYPES OF IV TO ORAL CONVERSIONS

1. **Sequential therapy:** This term describes the process of switching from a parenteral medicine to its equivalent oral medication. For instance, converting from 500mg azithromycin injection to a 500 mg azithromycin tablet.
2. **Switch therapy:** This term refers to the process of changing an IV medicine to a PO counterpart that belongs to the same class and is just as potent, but made of a different component. For instance, move from injecting 1 g of ceftriaxone (bis in die) to taking 200 mg of cefixime as a tablet
3. **Step down therapy:** Step-down therapy is the process of switching from an injectable drug to an oral drug of a different class or to a different drug within the same class, even if the frequency, dose, and spectrum of activity (in the case of antibiotics) may not be exactly the same. For instance, switching from injectable 1 g of cefotaxime to 500 mg of ciprofloxacin.^{33,3.}

Practical Methods for a Patient's Transition from IV To Oral Treatment

A hospital's implementation of an IV to oral switchover program is the first step in successfully transitioning a patient from IV to oral treatment. The establishment of such a guideline with the consent of the hospital's Pharmacy and Therapeutics committee is the sole duty of a clinical pharmacist, who must also oversee that the conversion is carried out in accordance with the guideline.

- A clinical pharmacist should first detect patients who take IV drugs, as well as their requirement for IV medications, and check for the indication.
- Second, regular follow-up is required to determine if the patient's clinical state is improving or not (WBC, vitals, culture report, patient's physical and mental health, etc.). If the patient qualifies for conversion, confirm that it was carried out.
- Inform the doctor about any patients who qualify for conversion but weren't converted in a timely manner.
- Make appropriate suggestions for the choice of an oral drug for conversion.
- Review the input from the doctors
- Monitor the patient's clinical status following the switchover and convert the patient back to parenteral medicine, if necessary.
- It is always good to confirm the physicians' understanding of and adherence to their recommendation for switching from IV to oral medication. For the same purpose, questionnaires are a common data collecting method.^{35,36,3.}

METHODS

➤ STUDY SITE

The study was conducted at Siddaganga Hospital & Research Centre, Tumakuru, Karnataka

➤ STUDY PERIOD

The study was conducted for a period of six months.

➤ STUDY DESIGN

An observational study

➤ STUDY POPULATION

A total number of 127 inpatients were included in the study.

➤ ETHICAL APPROVAL

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee of Siddaganga Hospital and Research Centre, Tumakuru, Karnataka.

IEC Ref No: SSCPT/SHRC/PPD/2022-23

➤ MATERIALS USED

- Data collection form
- Informed consent form

➤ STUDY CRITERIA

The study was carried out by considering the following inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion criteria:

- ✓ Both the genders.
- ✓ Hospitalized patients who are on Intravenous therapy for more than 2 days.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients admitted at ICU / referred to higher center for further follow-up.
- Patients on prophylactic antibiotic therapy.
- Pregnant women.
- Patient contradicted to oral therapy.

➤ DATA COLLECTION METHOD

This study involves assessing IV to oral antibiotic conversion in hospitalized patients at a tertiary care hospital. Data was collected using a structured profile form covering socio-demographic details, disease information, antibiotic usage, and types of the conversion process, including criteria considered. Ethical protocols will be adhered to through informed consent.

➤ STUDY PROCEDURES

It included 3 Phases;
PHASE 1: Designing the data collection form, used for the collection of data regarding IV to PO conversion drugs, and criteria used for conversion.

PHASE 2: After data collection, it is subjected to analyze the types and criteria used for conversion from IV to Oral antibiotics.

PHASE 3: Concluding the research report and presenting the result.

➤ STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The data were collected, compiled in MS EXCEL, and analyzed the type of conversion and the criteria for conversion. Statistical methods such as mean, median, and standard deviation are used. Graphical representations like bar graphs and tables have been used for visual representation of the analyzed data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The observational study was conducted in Sree Siddaganga Hospital and Research Centre, Tumakuru. A total of 127 patient's cases were enrolled in the study based on inclusion criteria. The demographics such as age, sex, diagnosis and treatment details from inpatient case sheets were recorded in semi structured profile form.

Distribution of Patient Based on Gender:

Total 127 patients were included during the study period. Table 1 provides the Gender distribution of the patients. The number of males, 70 (55.12%) were more compared to the number of females, 57 (44.88%).

Categorization Of Patients Based on Age

In our study maximum number of patients were found in the age group of above 60 years (33.07%), followed by 18-30 years (24.41%), 51-60 years (16.54%), 31-40 years (14.17%), 41-50 years (10.24%) and minimum number of patients were found in the age group of below 18 years (1.57%).

Distribution Of Patients Based on Department

127 samples were taken in 4 departments during the course of this study. Of these, 82.68% were from general medicine, 1.57% from Paediatrics, 2.36% from general surgery, and 13.39% from special wards which include pulmonology, nephrology, OBG, cardiology, orthopaedics, etc.

IV Antibiotics Administered in Inpatients

A total of 178 IV antibiotics were prescribed in 127 patients. Majority of the patients were prescribed class Cephalosporin (53.93%) followed by Nitroimidazoles (12.36%), combination (9.55%), aminoglycosides (7.87%), Fluoroquinolones (5.62%), Tetracyclines (4.49%), Lincosamides (3.37%), Polymyxin (1.12%), carbapenems (1.12%) and Oxazolidinones(0.56%)

Oral Antibiotics Prescribed in Patients

Cephalosporins (42.72%) class of antibiotic was most prescribed drug for discharge followed tetracyclines (30.10%), macrolides (5.83%), combination (4.85%), Fluroquinolones (3.88%), Oxazolidinones (3.88%), Aminoglycosides (2.91%), Nitroimidazoles (2.91%), Lincosamide(2.91%).

Type of Conversion:

Out of the 127 patients, 100 (78.74%) patients were converted and 27 (21.26%) patients were not converted. Types of conversion were done and among 100 converted cases mostly step-down 43 (43.00%) conversion takes place which is followed by switch 39 (39.00%) and sequential 18 (18.00%).

Categorization of Diseases Based on Conversion Therapy

Different disease conditions were observed during the study in which conversion was preferred. Most common conversions were observed in Systemic fever (40.00%) followed by Gastrointestinal infections (17.00%), RTI (16.00%), UTI (10.00%), Multiple organ infection (9.00%), and skin & soft tissue infection (8.00%).

Categorization of Antibiotics Based on Conversion Therapy

In sequential therapy the conversion from Inj. Doxycycline to Cap. Doxycycline (22.22%). In switch therapy the major conversion is Inj. Ceftriaxone to Tab. Cefixime (48.72%) and In Step-down therapy the major conversion is from Inj. Ceftriaxone to Tab. Doxycycline (30.23%).

LENGTH OF HOSPITAL STAY

The length of hospital stay (LOHS) was calculated for IV to oral converted and not converted cases. Mean LOHS for IV to Oral converted cases was 4.79. For non-converted cases, the Mean LOHS was 5.03. T test was applied to test the hypothesis that there is significant difference in length of hospital stay among converted and non-converted groups. The hypothesis was that Length of hospital stay in both converted and non-converted groups are same. T - Test revealed that there exists no statistically significant difference in length of hospital stay among converted and non-converted groups, which indicates that the hypothesis is true and hence it was concluded that length of hospital stay was unchanged in both converted and non-converted groups.

DURATION OF IV THERAPY

The duration of IV therapy was calculated and the mean duration of IV therapy for converted cases was found to be 3.83, and for non-converted cases was 4.22. T test was applied to test the hypothesis that there is significant difference in the duration of IV therapy among converted and non-converted groups. T-test revealed that there exists no statistically significant difference in duration of IV therapy among converted and non-converted groups, which indicates that the hypothesis is true and hence it was concluded that duration of IV therapy was unchanged in both converted and non-converted groups.

CRITERIA PREFERRED FOR CONVERSION

Out of 127 patients, 100 patients were converted from IV to Oral based on the following Criteria among them 61% of patients had completion of IV therapy, 2% of patients had Infusion-related adverse events, 95% of patients had undergone conversion after a significant decrease in signs and symptoms, in our study site we found 10% of patients had conversion of antibiotics from Broad spectrum to narrow spectrum, Both Patient stability & Plan for discharge were found to be 100% respectively.

CONCLUSION

Our study concludes that, most of the patients who were on intravenous antibiotics for more than 2 days were males compared to females. Majority of the patients were geriatrics. After the analysis of our data, we found that step-down therapy was the most preferred type of conversion. Criteria preferred for conversion were analyzed among converted cases. It was found that, most of the patients were converted after completion of IV therapy when the clinical stability is achieved. There were only a few antibiotics converted from broad spectrum to narrow spectrum. T-test revealed that there exists no statistical difference in length of hospital stay and duration of IV therapy among converted and non-converted groups. Physicians and clinical pharmacists are accountable for carefully going over patient data to determine which patients are eligible for the conversion. In order to enhance the practice of conversion, medical practitioners and clinical pharmacists should collaborate to work hand-in-hand.

LIMITATIONS

Various limitations exist in this study,

- ⇒ In the study we have only included data that shows IV to Oral conversion but, it doesn't account for the reconversion of Oral to IV due to various factors such as treatment failure, etc.
- ⇒ It would have been beneficial if the study included cost-effective analysis, but hindrances such as time restraints, complexity of the study, availability of the subjects etc. make it difficult to conduct.

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